

Optimism, Pessimism, and Their Relationship to The Level of Ambition Among Football Players

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Abstract

This study aimed to investigate the relationship between optimism, pessimism, and the level of ambition among football players. To achieve this, the researcher employed a descriptive-analytical approach, suitable for the nature of the study, on a sample of 75 players from three football clubs in Bouira State, selected randomly. For this purpose, the Seligman Scale for Optimism and Pessimism and the Ambition Level Scale developed by Maawoud and Abdel-Aziz were applied. The results revealed: A positive and significant correlation between optimism and the level of ambition. A negative and significant correlation between pessimism and the level of ambition. A high level of ambition among football players. In light of these findings, the researchers recommended the following: Designing guidance programs to develop optimism among various categories and levels. Constructing a scale to identify different types of optimism and pessimism. Establishing guidance centers in various sports clubs and activating their role to support players throughout their training and competitive journey. Utilizing the optimism and pessimism scale for other games and sports. Employing the ambition scale for other sports.

Keywords: *Optimism, Pessimism, Ambition, Football.*

INTRODUCTION AND IMPORTANCE OF THE STUDY

Sports psychology has witnessed a significant and remarkable leap, placing it at the forefront of sciences that focus on the facts and knowledge concerning athletes. This is due to the logical interaction between sports psychology and related psychological sciences that are connected to the individual or athlete. Ultimately, these interactions serve athletes by enhancing their capabilities, making them physically, mentally, and psychologically well-equipped to perform at the desired level.

Mental health is considered one of the key requirements for success in various fields, especially in light of the rapid advancements in different areas in the modern era, often referred to as the age of globalization, the age of technology, and the age of speed. These changes have brought about increased stress, anxiety, and the need for individuals to adapt to constantly changing circumstances.

This is reflected in Fahmy's (1979) definition of mental health as "the science of psychological adaptation or adjustment, which aims at the integration and cohesion of personality, self-acceptance, and the acceptance of others, leading to a sense of happiness and psychological well-being."

The study of optimism and pessimism has garnered significant attention from researchers in various psychological fields, due to the strong connection between these traits and an individual's mental health. Most theories have emphasized that optimism is associated with happiness, health, perseverance, achievement, and a positive outlook on life, while pessimism is linked to despair, failure, illness, and a negative view of life (Al-Ansari & Kazim, 2007, p. 113).

In this context, the World Health Organization for Mental Health (2004) states that optimism is a voluntary psychological process that generates thoughts and feelings of satisfaction, resilience, and self-confidence. This is the opposite of pessimism, which focuses only on the negative aspects of events, draining a person's energy and making them feel weak and lacking in motivation.

Hisham Mokhimer and Mohamed Abdel-Motie (1999) add that optimists tend to experience strong feelings of joy and satisfaction with themselves and life in general. Optimism is more closely related to positive emotions than negative ones, as optimists focus on the positive aspects of events and situations, while pessimists tend to exaggerate weaknesses and downplay strengths, advantages, and successes.

Success and the tasks we undertake depend largely on how optimistic we feel. This is achieved through expecting success, as long as there is a balance between demands and confidence in the ability to accomplish set goals. Optimists use their optimism as a starting point toward a more successful and brighter future (Mokhimer & Abdel-Motie, 2002, p. 41).

There is no doubt that optimism is one of the most important psychological traits, playing a vital role in our daily lives, our behaviors, and our relationships with others. Despite its significance in human life in general, and mental well-being in particular, interest in optimism is relatively recent. It has taken a prominent place in studies on personality, clinical psychology, and health psychology. Coaches have also recognized the importance of optimism as it reflects the individual's personality. An athlete or player needs to fill themselves with feelings of success to avoid being stuck in the failures they may face. This helps them to be full of enthusiasm and energy to achieve the best possible performance.

Thus, we understand the importance of optimism and positive thinking in events. People can choose how they think, and if they choose to think positively, they can eliminate many unwanted feelings that may hinder them from achieving their best potential. A positive mental attitude is closely linked to success in every field of life, and positive thinking is synonymous with optimism in every sense of the word. It involves seeing the beauty in everything, and positive thinking has a powerful impact on our mental state and our daily and future affairs (Al-Raqeeb, 2008, p. 7).

On the other hand, pessimism, which is the opposite of optimism, is a relatively modern psychological concept that has gained extensive research interest in health psychology and other psychological disciplines. Today, it is considered an important personality variable with a degree of relative stability (Badr Al-Ansari, 1998, p. 11).

Scheier and Carver (1992) define it as generalized outcome expectancies, which refer to perceived relationships between actions and their outcomes. These expectancies can be either positive (optimism) or negative (pessimism). Ahmed Abdel-Khaleq (1996, p. 6) defines pessimism as a negative expectation of future events, where the individual anticipates the worst, expecting bad outcomes, failure, and disappointment, while largely dismissing any other possibilities.

The Importance of the Study:

The importance of this research lies in studying optimism and pessimism and their relationship to the level of ambition, as it addresses the psychological aspects that affect football players during daily training or competition. Understanding these psychological states can contribute to the early identification of potential issues and the development of future solutions.

1. **Research Problem:** What is the relationship between optimism and pessimism with the level of ambition among football players?
2. **Research Hypothesis:** There is a relationship between optimism and pessimism with the level of ambition among football players.
3. **Research Objectives:** This study aims to achieve the following:
 - 1) To determine the relationship between optimism and the level of ambition among football players.
 - 2) To determine the relationship between pessimism and the level of ambition among football players.
 - 3) To assess the level of ambition among football players.

4. Definition of Concepts and Terms:

1) Optimism:

- **Linguistic Definition:** Optimism is a word or action that brings good fortune, and one becomes optimistic about something when they take it as a sign of hope. In contrast, pessimism stems from "shum," which means to bring bad luck, as in "a man brought bad luck to his people," and it implies expecting evil or bad outcomes (Ibn Manzur, n.d.).
- **Terminological Definition:** Carver and Scheier define optimism as a positive outlook on life and the belief that desires can be achieved in the future, along with the expectation that good things will happen rather than bad (Mohamed Shukri, 1999, p. 21).
- **Operational Definition:** In this study, the researchers define optimism theoretically as an individual's expectation that positive things will happen, while dismissing negative possibilities and striving to achieve them. Operationally, it is measured by the score that a player achieves on the optimism-pessimism scale used in the current study.

2) Pessimism:

- **Terminological Definition:** Badr Mohammed Al-Ansari defines pessimism as a negative expectation of future events, leading the individual to anticipate the worst, expecting evil, failure, and disappointment while dismissing any other outcomes to a large extent (Al-Ansari, 1998, p. 37).
- **Operational Definition:** The researchers define pessimism theoretically as a general expectation that negative events will occur in the future instead of positive ones, with little effort put forth towards achieving goals due to the belief that failure is inevitable. Operationally, it is measured by the score that a player achieves on the optimism-pessimism scale used in the current study.

3) Ambition:

- **Definition:** Ambition refers to a person characterized by optimism and the ability to set goals and legitimate means to achieve them.
- **Level of Ambition:** It is the individual's goal or ambition, which may form the main motivation to undertake a task. The level of ambition is the expected achievement that a person aims to reach in a given task, while being aware of their current performance (Bouftah, 2005, p. 80).
- **Operational Definition of Ambition:** The level of ambition can be defined as a relatively stable trait that varies from one person to another. It is associated with the individual's past experiences of success and failure and can increase or decrease depending on the surrounding circumstances.

5. Study Fields:

- 1) **Human Field:** The study was conducted on football players from clubs in Bouira Province.
- 2) **Spatial Field:** The study was applied at the stadiums of the football clubs.
- 3) **Time Field:** The study was carried out during the 2024/2023 sports season.

6. Theoretical Background:

The importance of the concepts of optimism and pessimism is evident in human life in general, and in psychological studies in particular. However, interest in these two concepts has only gained significant attention in the last two decades, attracting the focus of many researchers in the fields of personality, social psychology, clinical psychology, and health psychology (Shukri, 1999).

Scheier and Carver (1983) defined optimism as a positive outlook on life, with the belief in the likelihood of good or favorable outcomes rather than negative ones. In a more recent text from 1987, they added that optimism is an inherent trait within the individual, characterized by a general expectation of good or positive outcomes—essentially the expectation of positive results in future events (Abdel-Khaleq & Al-Ansari, 1995).

Abdel-Khaleq (2000) further defines optimism as a hopeful outlook towards the future, where the individual expects the best, anticipates good events, and aspires toward success. In contrast, pessimism is defined as a negative expectation of future events, leading the individual to anticipate the worst, expect bad outcomes, failure, and disappointment.

There is considerable debate among researchers regarding the relationship between optimism and pessimism, and at least two approaches to this relationship can be highlighted:

The first: that optimism and pessimism are two independent traits, but they are linked, meaning that each trait has a relatively independent continuum that combines the different degrees on the same trait, and each individual has a position on the optimism continuum that is independent of his position on the pessimism continuum, and each trait here is considered - independently - unipolar, starting from the lowest degree of optimism to the highest degree. The same thing is repeated - independently - for pessimism (Al-Ansari, 2003, p. 19)

Second: Optimism and pessimism are one trait, but it is bipolar, meaning that the continuum of this trait has two opposite poles, each individual has one focus on it, so that it falls between extreme optimism and extreme pessimism, and this includes that one individual - in general - cannot be, for example, very optimistic or very pessimistic, as he has one degree on the continuum (which is the same in the trait of extroversion - introversion (Al-Ansari, 2003)

Kelly (1974) Thorndike (1998) and Nunnally indicate that the trait can be represented by a continuous line of behavior through which we try to determine the individual's position on it in a specific trait he has, and the continuum means a straight line consisting of an infinite number of possible points that determine different locations for the measured trait. (Alam, 2002, pp. 22-23)

Based on this approach, measuring these two traits can be done using the optimism scale alone or the pessimism scale only, as the two traits are opposites, and the degree of one of them is the inverse of the other, as a high degree of optimism means a low degree of pessimism and vice versa, (Al-Ansari, 2003, p. 19)

The researcher adopted this approach because the content of the concepts of optimism and pessimism each reflects the other, and thus their effect on the individual's behavior in life goes in the same direction, and this seems acceptable from both theoretical and procedural perspectives, as the paragraphs of the scale prepared to measure pessimism do not differ in the content of their paragraphs from the scale prepared to measure optimism except in the direction of the paragraphs negatively or positively, and by applying this scale in this field, it is possible to obtain results that are easy to interpret.

The importance of studying the optimism-pessimism trait lies in the importance of its relationship with various aspects of the human personality, both normal and abnormal. Silkman's theory of invasion confirmed that the way we interpret things or events has the greatest impact on our current and future behavior more than their occurrence. It may have negative or good implications for our psychological and physical health (Al-Hajjar, 1989, p. 95).

Definition of Ambition

Ambition is defined in the context of the relationship between success and failure concerning one's level of aspiration. It refers to the goals or objectives a person aims to achieve in a particular task. Morton Deutsch defined ambition as "the goal that an individual works to achieve." The concept of ambition has significance when we can understand the extent to which achievable goals are realized.

Levels of Ambition

Researchers differentiate between three levels of ambition:

1) Level One: Ambition Aligned with Abilities

- At this level, ambition arises after a process of perception and evaluation in which an individual assesses their capabilities and readiness. The person acknowledges their actual level and abilities and then aspires to goals that are commensurate with these capabilities. This type of ambition is known as realistic or sound ambition, where the level of aspiration corresponds to the individual's potential.

2) Level Two: Ambition Below Abilities

- In this level, an individual possesses high and significant potential but fails to establish a level of ambition that matches these abilities. In other words, their level of ambition is lower than their capabilities, which may prevent them from realizing their full potential.

3) Level Three: Ambition Exceeding Abilities

- This level is the opposite of the previous one, where an individual's level of ambition is higher than their capabilities. In this case, there is a discrepancy between ambition and ability. For example, a consistently unsuccessful athlete who aspires to succeed and qualify for the Olympics represents what is known as unrealistic or unhealthy ambition (Souhair, 1999, pp. 191-192).

Determinants of Athletic Ambition

Experiences of Success and Failure:

The degree of an individual's success or failure in a task undoubtedly impacts their performance in subsequent tasks. If a person experiences success in their work and achieves a sense of internal psychological satisfaction, they may begin to think of new endeavors that surpass their current achievements and align with the level of excellence and success they have attained. Success, according to the Sillamy dictionary, "activates creative forces and becomes the enhancer that drives one to surpass themselves by raising their level of ambition" (Bouftah, 2005, p. 42).

Reward and Punishment:

The concept of reward and punishment is one of the most commonly used ideas in education, industry, and daily interactions. Thorndike was among the first to apply this concept in his experimental work with animals to understand various behavioral responses. Positive reinforcement, such as expressions of thanks, encouragement, appreciation, and financial rewards, represents the principle of reward in both its material and moral forms. Individuals receive rewards or face consequences based on their daily actions, whether at school, home, or in society. If an individual accomplishes a task according to predetermined standards, they receive a reward; conversely, failure leads to punishment (Krajah, 1997, p. 197).

Cognitive Abilities:

Intelligence: Intelligence is regarded as one of the most significant cognitive abilities that researchers and psychologists have focused on due to its impact on psychological and physical well-being. There is a relationship between intelligence and ambition level, as intelligence influences ambition in various ways (Ben Brika, 2003-2004, p. 35).

Creativity: Creativity is a mental activity that generates new, original, and unconventional ideas, leading to extraordinary solutions for the problems individuals face. It saves time and effort, and these ideas can solve many of the challenges encountered. Creativity impacts ambition by enabling individuals to adopt new, distinctive goals and produce a greater number of unique individuals and objectives that align with their creative abilities (Bouftah, 2005, previously cited, p. 96).

Individual Intelligence and Emotional Stability

An individual's intelligence helps them understand themselves, assess their capabilities and tendencies, and recognize the different skills and traits required for various tasks. As a

result, their level of ambition is not far removed from reality, remaining within their abilities. When a person achieves their ambitions, they experience success, which enhances their self-esteem. Conversely, if they cannot reach their goals, they may feel failure and inadequacy, leading to a decline in self-worth. Thus, the level of ambition serves as a standard by which an individual measures their success or failure in their pursuits, and it changes depending on their experiences of success or failure in achieving their goals.

Level of Ambition in Sports

The level of ambition is a relatively stable trait that distinguishes individuals in their attempts to reach a certain level, which aligns with their psychological makeup and reference framework. It is determined by the experiences of success and failure that an individual has encountered. Based on this, two definitions of the level of ambition in the sporting context can be presented (Ibrahim, 1993, p. 72):

- 1) **First Definition:** It is the level of physical or skill performance that the athlete expects to achieve in their sport.
- 2) **Second Definition:** It is the goal that the athlete strives to reach based on the conditions they face, including their successes and failures in achieving their objectives.

The level of sporting ambition varies depending on the type of sports activity and differs from one athlete to another. Ambition is considered one of the essential components of personality, representing a level of performance, skill, physical fitness, or a general sports goal that the athlete aims to achieve.

As athletes engage in different sports activities, they set their ambitions according to the nature of those activities. This is because the level of sporting ambition is a fundamental component of personality, varying from athlete to athlete and from one sport to another. Thus, the level of sporting ambition is merely the performance level an individual strives to achieve, heavily relying on prior experience and positive feedback.

An aspiring athlete aims to raise their level of ambition following success but not to an extent that is unattainable. They become aware of their true capabilities and limitations, as well as their competitors' levels. Additionally, other individuals, such as coaches and parents, play a role in setting goals and building the level of ambition. Coaches are expected to accurately understand the athlete's objectives and support them in training to help achieve those goals and succeed.

METHODOLOGICAL PROCEDURES OF THE STUDY

In this section, we will address the methodology of the field study, focusing on the appropriate approach, explaining the tools and methods used for data collection, and analyzing the results. We will also highlight the relationship of these procedures to the hypotheses and theoretical framework, as well as explain the statistical techniques employed to analyze and discuss the findings.

- 1) **Adopted Approach:** Given the nature and progression of the subject, a descriptive-analytical approach was implemented due to its suitability for the topic.
- 2) **Study Population:** The study population consists of all football players in the provincial league of Bouira for the sports season (2024/2023).

- 3) **Research Sample:** In this context, the sample refers to the segment of the study population from which data will be collected. It represents a portion of the entire population and is often used to infer results applicable to the larger group. In our study, the sample was composed of three clubs, totaling 75 players, which constitutes approximately 25% of the population.
- 4) **Study tool:** This study aims to identify the relationship between optimism and pessimism and its relationship to the level of ambition among football players. In line with the objectives of the study and in order to verify its hypotheses in the theoretical aspect and what is required for data and results that the researcher relies on to achieve the objectives of the study, the researchers chose: A- Optimism and pessimism scale: prepared by (1989) Dember et al. To measure optimism and pessimism, it was translated and standardized in the Arabic environment by “Magdy Mohamed El-Dessouki” (2001). The scale consists of (56) phrases, including (18) phrases to measure optimism, and the same to measure pessimism, in addition to (20) phrases repeated in other forms in order to hide the purpose of the scale. To prepare the scale in its Arabic form, “Magdy Mohamed El-Dessouki” (2002) translated its phrases and was keen to have the translation into Arabic with the greatest degree of neutrality and objectivity so that the meaning does not change in any way. As we mentioned previously, the scale contains two sub-scales to measure optimism and pessimism, and therefore there are phrases that indicate optimism and others indicate pessimism, which are: The phrases that represent the sub-scale of optimism are: 7-11 – 12 – 15 – 17 – 19 – 21 – 23 – 28 – 29 – 33 – 37 – 43 – 46 - 47 - 52 - 56. The phrases that represent the pessimism sub-scale are: 2- 4 - 5 - 8 - 10 - 14 20 - 26 - 31 - 34 - 36 - 39 - 42 - 44 - 49 - 51 - 54. These responses were assigned graded weights as follows: I completely agree (4), I agree (3), I disagree (2), I completely disagree (1). Algebraic addition is used to calculate the total score that the examinee obtains on each sub-scale separately. Since the phrases of each scale are (18), and the choices are four choices, the minimum s B-Ambition scale in the sports field: The researcher used the ambition scale, which consisted of 36 phrases distributed over four dimensions, which are:

1. Optimism dimension, 12 phrases, which are: (6 7 9 11 12 13 18 19 24 25 26 32).
2. The ability to set goals dimension, 10 phrases, which are: (1 2 3 4 8 10 14 16 17 36).
3. Acceptance of the new dimension, 8 phrases, which are: (15 28 29 30 31 33 34 35).
4. Tolerance of frustration dimension, 6 phrases, which are: (5 20 21 22 23 27).

The response scale for these statements consists of (4) responses prepared using the four-point scale method, which are: always (4) degrees, often (3), sometimes two degrees, and rarely one degree. Thus, the response ranges between (1-4) degrees for positive items, while for negative statements, which are: (6 23 30 32 36), it is as follows: always one degree, often two degrees, sometimes (3) degrees, and rarely (4) degrees. (Moawad, Mohamed Abdel Tawab, Abdel Azim Sayed, 2005)

Validity of the scale: The level of quality that the research reaches does not depend on the correct testing of the sample or the rational testing of the most appropriate research methods, but rather on the efficiency of the tools that the researcher uses to collect data. Validity scales are considered among the most important scales that the research is keen to take into account when conducting the research to ensure the factor of objectivity so that subjective aspects can be controlled.

Validity of the arbitrators: The two scales were presented in their initial form to a group of university professors specializing in the sciences and technologies of physical and sports activities, where they expressed their opinions and observations regarding the suitability of the scales' paragraphs, the extent of the paragraphs' suitability to each field of the scales, and their clarity. core is (18), and the maximum score is (72).

Presentation of study results: There is a relationship between optimism, pessimism and the level of ambition among football players

A- Regarding the relationship between optimism and the level of ambition among football players

Significance level	Ambition level	
0.01	0.887	optimism

From the table, we notice that there is a strong positive direct relationship between optimism and the level of ambition at a significance level of 0.01, meaning that the greater the optimism, the greater the level of ambition among football players. This result can be interpreted as optimism playing an important role in our psychological life, in our behaviors, in our relationships with others, and in the plans we make to undertake in the near and distant future.

We do not exaggerate if we say that all positive activities in our lives, whether they are thoughts, emotions, or actions, are linked (in one way or another) to what works in our psychological system of optimism, and what goes on in our minds of thoughts and what is prevalent in our hearts of feelings, but it affects to the greatest extent our perception of external reality. (Asaad, 1986, p. 32).

This is what Weinstein went to, that most people assume that optimism includes their future expectations of events, and depends on that and is linked to it, that the observer of current events is optimistic if the events are happy and pessimistic if the events are miserable, and perhaps some people claim that they are pessimistic about things that are not unlikely to happen, so as soon as an hour, a day, or a week passes, their feeling is realized and a disaster occurs, and vice versa, and people explain that by previous vision or anticipation of the future And expect it, and thus we find the individual has begun to realize the future with what it includes of good and evil, as he responds emotionally with optimism in the case of happy and good events ((Weinstein, 1980P 806

Optimism is a tendency and cognitive structure consisting of a general belief in positive results based on rational estimates of the person's preference for the possibility of success and a belief and faith in personal competence. Optimism is not hope, as it is an expectation that a certain result will happen to a person who will recover from an illness. The dictionary definition of it is "a tendency to expect the best possible result." The importance of optimism. Optimism occupies an important position in s Optimism is not a medicine used to cure all diseases. However, it can protect against psychological diseases such as depression, anxiety, and despair. It also increases the level of achievement and supports physical formation. Optimism is considered a very cheerful mental state that afflicts an optimistic person.

The importance of optimism stems from the fact that the Islamic religion calls for it and rejects pessimism. As the Prophet, may God bless him and grant him peace, said in the hadith narrated by Al-Bukhari (Be optimistic about good and you will find it).

Optimism is also an important stimulating factor in the life of the individual, as it makes its owner accept life, strive in it, and enjoy psychological, physical, and mental health. He is a sound personality and able to overcome any pressures or problems.

That is, the athlete is in a state of optimism through his awareness of the different skills and different preparations in sports training that lead to improving performance, and this indicates psychological characteristics such as high self-confidence in capabilities and the player's love and passion for football and the future of practicing it, and that the scope of optimism goes beyond the love of winning matches to fame, brilliance and success. This indicates that football players feel a degree of optimism, and this indicates the strength and solidity of the football player's personality.

Through the distinctive optimism trait they have, it helps them with a high ability to endure hardship and frustration, tolerance and the ability to find alternative ideas and even future dreams. Despite what surrounds him, hope remains with him, and he always searches for solutions to the problems he faces and appears optimistic about the future. The feeling of optimism in the athlete means ambition that leads to high morale and to increasing the athlete's ability to build ambitious future ideas and projects.

The results of this study agreed with the results of the study of Abdul Nasser Abdul Rahim Al-Qudomi, (2015) The level of optimism among players of collective sports teams in Palestinian universities. The study concluded that The overall level of optimism among the study sample members was high, as the response percentage reached 76.20%. The results showed that there were no statistically significant differences in the level of optimism among university sports team players.ome aspects of life.

A- Regarding the relationship between pessimism and the level of ambition among football players

Significance level	Ambition level	
0.01	0.437-	Pessimism

In the table, we notice that there is an inverse relationship between pessimism and the level of ambition at the significance level of 0.01, i.e. the greater the pessimism, the lower the level of ambition among football players and vice versa.

The researchers explain this result by saying that there is an inverse relationship between pessimism and the level of ambition. The increase in pessimism and the decrease in optimism led to a decrease in the level of ambition among football players.

The expectation of difficulties and the lack of horizon among football players towards the future, impatience and failure to satisfy their psychological needs, whether in training, matches or the club as a whole, made them anxious about their future, frustrated and dissatisfied with their lives.

This result confirms what Al-Ansari went to: Continuous failure to deal with the social environment leads to a constant feeling of pessimism and despair and the disappearance of positive expectations and hopes for change and the realization of the person that he is a negative product of the environment (Al-Ansari, 1998, p. 18)

CONCLUSIONS

By processing and analyzing the results of the study sample, we conclude the following:

- 1) There is a positive and significant relationship between optimism and the level of ambition.
- 2) There is a negative and significant relationship between pessimism and the level of ambition.

Conclusion of the study:

The topic of optimism and pessimism is considered one of the important topics in psychology because of their impact on the behavior of athletes and their psychological state; when all the player's needs are met in training and competition, he feels optimistic and that he can achieve his goals, which makes him feel happy and relaxed, and thus motivates him to accept life with enthusiasm, perseverance and desire, and takes into account the possibilities of success and sets in light of that a legitimate ambition in the future in terms of goals and strives positively to achieve them. However, if the individual fails to satisfy his needs, he feels pessimistic and that he cannot achieve his goals, which makes him feel despair, loss of hope and frustration, and accepts life with lukewarmness, hesitation and expectation of failure. He is always skeptical about success, which may lead to his disorder and lack of desire for ambition or weakness. Study Recommendations:

After completing the study and reaching the research results that were extracted above, we suggest some points that may be studies in the future:

- 1) Benefit from the research results in the process of psychological counseling and educational guidance for football players.
- 2) Conduct a follow-up study to investigate the development of the concept of optimism and pessimism among cubs
- 3) Provide guidance programs based on optimism, building confidence, goals and ambition.
- 4) Evaluate the levels of ambition and building goals among players.
- 5) Conduct studies on the relationship between optimism and pessimism and the level of ambition and other psychological variables such as: sports identity, sportsmanship, creativity, self-confidence, self-esteem, and self-concept among athletes.

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